

FEA USING DESIGN OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUE FOR AN APPLICATION OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS TO AUTOMOBILE BODY STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) is now in the spotlight because of its advantageous properties for mass production of automobile. If the structural design using CFRTP is optimized and required mechanical properties are satisfied, CFRTP can be used in automobile frame structures in the same way as a steel which has been established for mass production.

In order to consider the optimal structural design, the finite element method (FEM) using topology, shape and size optimization is known to be an effective tool. In our study, we focus on basic part and external forces in automobile frame structures, and lead that the structural design of CFRTP is lighter than that of steel under the same stiffness by optimization in FEM.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve reduction of automobile weight, fiber reinforced composites have been applied to a number of automobile components because of having high-stiffness and high-strength to weight ratio. A new type of thermoplastic composite materials, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) which is composed of surface treated carbon fiber (TR50S provided by Mitsubishi Rayon) and maleic-acid modified polypropylene (developed by TOYOBO) [1, 2], has been developed for the purpose of applying to automobile frame structures in order to achieve reduction of weight.

In this paper, we use these materials and consider the optimal structural design for basic S-shape frame structure. In the first concept phase, we come up with the optimal geometry required in an available design space as a solution of shape and topology optimization, of course, in consideration of specific constraint and ability of molding. The solution can become the stiffest design possibly under the same weight before the optimization. In the next tuning phase, the geometry based shape and topology optimization get lighter through parametric process with thickness using the size optimization, in addition with fiber direction and how to stack laminate of orthotropic material such as unidirectional material.

2 OBJECTIVE AND APPROACH OF OPTIMIZATION

Our objective is to come up with the lighter structural design of CFRTP half than that of steel, of course with the same performance as that of steel (see Figure 1). And it may be the specific structural design for only CFRTP if designed in the constraints of the specific molding and joining method for CFRTP. It is called composite design.

Figure 1: Target image of lightweight effect and performance.

Our approach shown in Figure 2 is to evaluate the balance between the lightweight effect and the performance applying CFRTP by using various optimization in FEM software. Then there are three main types which are topology optimization, shape optimization and size optimization. In the general structural optimization, the selection or the combination of them depends on purposes. Given optimization, the following four formations should be defined, design variables, responses, constraints and an objective function.

1. The design variables are things that influences the performance of the structure, for example, the thickness and shape dimensions.
2. The responses mean any value that is changed in the structural analysis, or is output. The typical things of responses are strain, stress, and compliance. Responses are used to evaluate the performance of the structure.
3. The constraints mean tolerance of the design variables and the responses. Each design variable and response is constrained with an allowed minimum and maximum value. The typical things of constraints are maximum allowed stress, compliance, or minimum allowed thickness.
4. The objective function is a response used to decide how good a design is. In an optimization formulation, objective functions used typically are mass and compliance. The objective function is usually to be minimized (minimization problem).

Figure 2: Flow of optimization.

3 INVESTIGATED MODEL AND THE BOUNDARY CONDITION

Figure 3 shows the model of the S-shape frame structure imaged the automobile frame structure. It has a structure that jointed three plates, such as to sandwich single plate between two hat-sections. Total length of the S-shape frame structure is 800 mm. The other dimensions are shown in Figure 3. As boundary conditions, the end of the S-shape frame structure receives load when its other end is fixed.

Robustness to load from the multi-directions is one of the features required for the automobile frame structure unlike that of the aircraft. Because there is a possibility that automobile itself receives load from multi-directions, the structural design has toughness not only against load from one direction, but also against load from any direction. In order to evaluate the robustness, the S-shape frame structure receives load from three directions. One condition is full rap loading condition assuming the front collision, another condition is to receive load from the oblique 45 degrees, and the last condition is to receive load from right side assuming the side collision. In this study, the weight of three conditions is considered with the all same weight, strictly speaking it might in fact different. The size of the load should be very small in the case of evaluating the stiffness. Therefore, it is 100 N.

Figure 3: S-shape frame structure that jointed three parts and boundary condition with external load.

4 MATERIAL INFORMATION AND SPECIFICATION

Two types of CFRTP are used in this study. One is a laminated constitution of chopped CF/PP tapes dispersed at random in in-plane pattern. The other is a laminated constitution of unidirectional CF/PP prepreg. The former type is called CTT (carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics), the latter type is called UD in this study. The left of Table 1 shows each composition of CTT laminate or UD laminate respectively. From mechanical aspect, the UD laminate has an orthotropic property and the CTT laminate has an in-plane isotropic property. Since UD has stiff property only in one direction, it is reasonable to use as a reinforcement of the CTT. As the material for the comparison of CFRTP, the 780 MPa steel that is used in automobile frame structures is shown in the table.

	<i>CTT laminate</i>	<i>UD laminate</i>	<i>Material property</i>			
<i>Carbon Fiber</i>	<i>TR50S</i>	<i>TR50S</i>		<i>STEEL</i>	<i>CTT</i>	<i>UD</i>
<i>Volume Fraction</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Density(g/cm³)</i>	7.84	1.35	1.33
<i>Tape size</i>	<i>Length:35mm</i> <i>Width:15mm</i>	<i>Continuous</i>	<i>Elastic modulus (GPa)</i>	<i>E₁</i>	211	32
<i>Matrix resin</i>	<i>Acid modified polypropylene</i>	<i>Acid modified polypropylene</i>		<i>E₂</i>	211	32
<i>Mechanical property</i>	<i>In-plane isotropic</i>	<i>Orthotropic</i>		<i>G₁₂</i>	81	12
				<i>G₁₃</i>	81	2
				<i>G₂₃</i>	81	2
				<i>Poisson's ratio</i>	<i>ν₁₂</i>	0.3
				<i>Strength (MPa)</i>	<i>σ_{1y}</i>	780
					<i>σ_{2y}</i>	315
					<i>σ_{1c}</i>	21
					<i>σ_{1c}</i>	780
					<i>σ_{2c}</i>	240
						70

Table 1: Material property and parameters of CTT laminate and UD laminate.

5 COMPARISON BEFORE OPTIMIZATION

Before studying the lightweight effect of structural design using CFRTP against that of steel focused on S-shaped frame structure, the first comparison between CFRTP and steel is made under the same outline with S-shaped frame structure, although the thickness of CFRTP is different from that of steel. The CFRTP selected as comparison of steel is CTT that have the same mechanical property as steel, which is in-plane isotropic. As a prerequisite of steel, the plate thickness of steel is 1 mm, and joining method is spot welding, as well as used in the actual automobile frame structure. The interval between the spot welding is 25mm along the jointed flange line, and the diameter of the spot welding is 10mm. On the other hand, the joining method of CTT is the vibration welding which joints the entire flange area. The stiffness of the vibration welding area is 2 GPa, and its strength is 20 MPa according to the material property of the resin. The maximum thickness of CTT is 6 mm, the minimum thickness is 2 mm because of molding constraint. To be half of the mass of the structural design using steel, the thickness of CTT is 3 mm. The indexes to be evaluated in FEM study are the following things, mass and compliance. As a definition, compliance has a relation of an inverse proportion with stiffness.

Figure 4 shows comparison about stiffness and weight between steel and CTT for initial structural design. Of course, the structural design using CTT is lighter half than that of steel. But, the structural design using CTT has lower stiffness than that of steel under all conditions. From this fact, only entire increase of thickness can't avoid increase of weight in order to increase stiffness of structural design using CTT, or outline change of initial shape. Therefore, if the size of the thickness of each part in keeping the outline is optimized to the condition, and if the outline changes to optimized new shape in the constraint, it is possible that objection of weight reduction is achieved. As mentioned at the beginning, our target is more than 50% with the same performance as that of steel.

Figure 4: Comparison with mass and stiffness.

6 TOPOLOGY AND SHAPE ANALYSIS IN THE CONCEPT PHASE

As a prerequisite, the outer space from the initial outline of S-shape frame structure cannot be used because of comparison with structural design of steel. In other words, the design space which can be considered is only space inside from the initial outline. Under this constraint, the two approaches is possible. One approach is to optimize the inner space of the initial outline. In particular, the initial position and shape of centerplate may change better shape and position. Because centerplate is the relatively higher degree of design freedom with centerplate than with the other two hat-sections. It means that line of joint surface may change.

As an approach for optimizing the inner space of the S-crank structural design, the method of topological analysis is the most adequate for the optimization. In the formation for topology analysis, the design variables is the volume ratio of the inner space, moreover the constraint is constant of the ratio. The objective function is minimization of compliance (see Figure 5). In other words, it means leading the stiffest structural design under the constrained volume ratio in the design space. The 2 mm layer on outline is not included in the design space, that is, it is keeping as constant in optimization.

Figure 5: The formation for topology analysis.

Figure 6 shows the results of topology optimization under 10% and 20% volume ratio of the design space, where 10 or 20% of the volume except for 2 mm of the outside layer can be change their position. Red parts in the figure indicate a sensitive parts for the structural stiffness, hence red parts become thicker while blue parts become thinner. Their results show a little different. When optimizing the structural design on the basis of these results, it is important to image real design in molding technology. For example, considered on the basis of the result with 10%, the reinforcing structure such as ribs may be imaged really. On the one hand, considered on the basis of result with 20%, it is reasonable to change the jointing line. Judging from the difficulty of the molding technology, it is realistic to change the structural design and the position of joint surface which are based on the result with 20%.

Figure 6: The result of topology optimization under 10% and 20% volume ratio of the inner space.

Figure 7 shows the structural design modified on the base of the result of the 20%. The next approach is to optimize the width of the flange. The flange is required for jointing of three plates. The lowering of the entire structural stiffness is influenced by the stiffness of the joint surface which has basically mechanical properties of the resin of CTT. In general, the entire structural stiffness increases as the width of flange is wider. But the structure itself become heavy conversely and there is problem of over constraint with the design space. This paradox also applies about the thickness of the structure. Therefore, in the performance compatible premise of parts, the optimal thickness of each part and the optimal width of flange is to be considered. As the approach for optimizing the width of the flange and the thickness of each plate, the method of shape and size analysis is adequate for the optimization. In the formation, the design variables is the width of the flange for shape analysis, and the thickness of each plate for size analysis. The response is mass and compliance, moreover the constraint is that the compliance of the structural design using CTT is lower than that of steel, that the width of the flange is from 5 mm to 25 mm, and that thickness of each plate is from 2 mm to 6 mm. The objective function is minimization of mass. It means realizing the lightest structure using CTT under the same performance as that of steel.

By shape and size optimization, the width of the flange and the thickness of each plate was adjusted to optimal parameter as you can see in Figure 8. As a result, weight of the structure after optimization showed 2.17 kg, which indicated that the weight reduction of 49.5 % was achieved in keeping the same stiffness as the structure using steel (see Figure 9). Based on these results, the shape of vibration welding area need to spread more widely near the fixed point. Additionally, judging from the difference of the optimal thickness in three parts, centerplate may contribute to the entire structural stiffness relatively.

Figure 7: The formation for shape and size analysis from topology optimization.

Figure 8: The results of shape optimization (L) and size optimization (R).

Figure 9: Comparison of mass and stiffness after optimization.

7 TOPOMETRY ANALYSIS IN TUNING PHASE

To achieve the weight reduction of more than 50 %, the following approach is reasonable, which optimal thickness is set for each area in one part. Variable thickness can be applied for each area in one part using CFRTP as molding technology of CFRTP unlike that of steel. If the optimization applying variable thickness for each area in each part is performed for the structure led by topology analysis, the result has potential to achieve the weight reduction of more than 50 % of the initial structural design using steel. As an approach for optimizing thickness for each area, the method of topometry analysis is adequate for the optimization. Free size analysis which is used generally as topometry analysis is different from normal size analysis. It can calculate various optimal thickness for each area in a single part. That is, free size analysis can calculate the optimal thickness for each finite element, not for each part. The formation for the optimization is the same as shape and size optimization shown in above, the design variables, the constraint, the response and the objective function.

The right of Figure 10 shows the result of topometric optimization under constraint that thickness changes from 2 mm to 6 mm. In each part, the distributed thickness by the optimization was very extreme. Especially, the side area of the two hat sections was required thickness compared to the other area. In fact, it is impossible to apply this numerical thickness distribution directly to the structure because of considering molding technology. That is, it is realistic that one part is divided to several areas of which each thickness is different on the base of the thickness distribution led by the optimization. In this case, the top area of part and the side area of the part is divided, although they are consolidated each other.

Figure 11 shows the structural design divided to two area for hat sections on the base of topometric optimization. Like the optimization shown in the previous phase, the next approach is to optimize the width of the flange and the thickness of each part in the performance compatible premise of parts. As the approach for optimizing the width of the flange and the thickness of each plate, the method of shape and size analysis is adequate for the optimization. The formation for the optimization is the same as shape and size optimization shown in the previous.

Figure 10: The formation and the result for topometry analysis.

Figure 11: The formation for shape and size analysis from topometric optimization.

By shape and size optimization, the width of the flange and the thickness of each plate was adjusted to optimal parameter as you can see in Figure 12. As a result, weight of the structure after optimization was 1.98 kg, which indicated that the weight reduction of 53.9% was achieved in keeping the same stiffness as the structure using steel.

Figure 12: The result of size optimization (L) and comparison of mass after optimization (R).

8 HYBRID MATERIAL DESIGN IN TUNING PHASE

To make more and more light-weight structure, applicability of a hybrid structure composed of CTT and UD is attractive. This is a superiority on molding technology of CFRTP. However UD have orthotropic material property. Though mechanical properties of UD in fiber direction are superior as three times higher than CTT, the mechanical properties in transversal direction are only one-tenth of CTT. Hence, it is reasonable that UD is used as a reinforcement of CTT. Thus, if applying the hybrid structure, the orientation of the UD ply must be optimized to boundary conditions as you can see in Figure 13. Speaking further, as the result of control with the stiffness of the structure by adjusting the orientation of UD to the boundary conditions, CTT may have lower thickness relatively. Therefore, more weight reduction is potential.

Figure 13: The formation and the result for size analysis of angle of UD ply.

Figure 14 shows the result of size optimization of the angle. The design variables is the orientation of UD ply, and the objective function is minimization of compliance. As a result, the optimization shows that the stiffness becomes highest by aligning the direction of the UD to longitudinal direction of the S-crank frame structure.

The next approach is to optimize the width of the flange and the thickness of CTT and UD in each part, fixed the optimal direction of UD orientation. Here, the upper limit of the thickness of UD ply is

the following three patterns, 1.5 mm, 1.0 mm, and 0.5 mm. And, the pattern A is 1.5 mm, the pattern B is 1.0 mm, and the pattern C is 0.5 mm. By shape and size optimization, the width of the flange and the thickness of each plate was adjusted to optimal parameter as you can see in Figure 15. As a result, weight of the structure after optimization was 1.73 kg in pattern A, 1.76 kg in pattern B, and 1.84 kg in pattern C respectively. From these results, weight reduction of 59.8% was achieved at most in keeping the same stiffness as the structure using steel.

Figure 14: The result of size optimization about the pattern A.

Figure 15: Comparison of mass and stiffness after optimization.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this research, weight-lightening possibility of S-crank frame structure was investigated by using optimization tools in FEM software. We focused on a structural stiffness as a target performance, and conducted optimal design to obtain the lightest structure using CFRTP.

At first, we changed initial outline of structure to the best one by topology optimization, and optimized the width of flange and thickness of whole structure by shape and size optimization. As a result, weight reduction of 53.9% was achieved comparing to steel one with the same stiffness.

Additionally, we tried further weight reduction by using a hybrid structure composed of CTT and UD. Optimal orientation of UD ply according to the loading conditions were adjusted first by size optimization. After that, thickness of CTT and UD are optimized by shape and size optimization. As a result, weight reduction of about 60% was achieved.

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